

Participatory software development via Living Labs: A case of Deajeon

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Abstract

Over the past few years in Korea (Republic of Korea), demands for welfare policies to prepare for an aging society and to secure a social security have been grown. Responding to the growing needs of people, Korea Government is running the research and development (R&D) projects using Information Technologies (eg. Software, IoT, AI, big data etc.) to make public services which resolve the social issues efficiently. The Living labs is considered as one of research and development methods, which aims to close the gap between technical and social innovation by enhancing collaboration between different relevant stakeholders (Kopp, Haider, & Preinesberger, 2017, p.61). Hence, NIPA (National IT Industry Promotion Agency) has tried applying the Living Labs on software development projects to make software solutions for local community. Compared to the conventional research and development projects, Living Labs has a slower pace spending more time and efforts on communication with relevant stakeholders (issue exploration, demand definition etc.), but it's more effective way to reflect concrete demands of users on research and development projects.

Keywords: *Living Labs, software development, co-creation, software solution, stakeholders*

1 Introduction

The Ministry of Science and ICT (referred to “MSIT”) is responsible for the policies on Science and Information communication technology research and development in Korea (The Republic of Korea). National IT Industry Promotion Agency (referred to “NIPA”) is a government affiliated organization that makes action plans for the ICT Research and Development Projects and supports organizations who conduct ICT research and development projects - such as research institutions, universities, business entities, local government agencies - to put MSIT policies into practice.

Recently, NIPA has initiated the research and development projects using Living Lab methodology, which use software technology to resolve issues for a local community. The projects are in progress as a pilot. Based upon the result of it, NIPA is planning to expand the adoptions of Living Lab methodology to the software research and development project. In every project using Living Labs, the participations of different stakeholders are crucial factors. Among the projects NIPA supports, with the case of Deajeon, this paper explains how to apply Living Lab methodology to software research and development project, and how to draw the stakeholders’ collaboration on Living Lab process.

R&D toward Technological Advancement- Versus Social Innovation

Since 1990s, Korea Government has invested huge amount of funds on Information Technology (eg. software, big data, cloud, IoT, artificial intelligence etc.) research and development. Majority of them led by technology professionals - such as research institutes, universities, corporations etc. - , and aim to produce economic value by developing advanced technologies dealing with industrial issues.

In the 2000s, people have been concerned about social welfares for an aging society and a daily living safety. Responding to these national demands, Korea Government has tried to take advantage of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) to make a better life of its people. Government driven projects to develop public services using ICT were carried out in a wide range of areas, such as healthcare, education, emergency management, food sanitation etc. However, the outcomes of them had difficulties in applying to people’s real life and commercialization. The conventional research and development projects are led by technology professionals, such as research institute, universities, corporations etc. In such way, embracing the opinions of ordinary people to the development project was limited. The majority of public service end-users is ordinary people. Many of them are not familiar with cutting-edge technologies, and reluctant to try new things required much learnings how to use. First and most important thing to ordinary people is not whether up-to-date

technologies are applied in it, but whether the services (the result of development project) could resolve their inconveniences or not.

Eriksson, Niitamo, and Kulkki (2005, p.6) and Lepik, Krigul, and Terk (2010, p.1091) consider the Living Labs as a research and development methodology, which aims to close the gap between technical and social innovation and to enhance collaboration between different relevant stakeholders. In this regard, NIPA went into applying Living Labs to software service development project to resolve social issues of local governments. Considering that Living Labs was not familiar to employee of local government agencies, NIPA provided a three-month “Design Thinking” and Living Labs methodology training program to local government agencies’ employee beforehand, in 2016. After the training program, NIPA encouraged those trainees to become Living Lab facilitators and to do applying Living Labs to their software research and development projects. As a trial basis, Living Labs has been implemented to a part of their projects.

Deajeon City Case: The Household Wastes Treatment in Old Town

Deajeon is a distinctive area that national research and development institutes are clustered. People of Deajion have a positive attitude to adopt technologies relatively. Deajeon City wanted to resolve the inconvenience of citizens efficiently using software technologies. Deajeon Information & Culture Industry Promotion Agency (referred to as “DICA”) is a local government affiliated organization that executes the ICT Research and Development policies for Deajeon City.

Since 2016, NIPA and DICA have conducted “Soft Town” Program which aims to enhance Deajeon citizens living by applying software technologies. NIPA and DICA agreed that the conventional way of research and development was not fit to deal with social issues, and not suitable for embracing opinions of people sufficiently. In that regard, they decided to adopt Living Labs to a part of their software service development project in “Soft Town” Program from 2017.

Software Service Development via Living Labs

To gather the opinions of citizens and made an effective solution to citizen, NIPA and DICA would like to make process software development project along with local people with a systematic research and development framework. iLab.o’s methodology is based on the social construction of technology framework, which suggests that technology is shaped by the user (in this case, “deajeon citizens”) and highlights the importance of context in the process of endowing technologies with social meanings (Almirall, Lee, and Wareham, 2012, p.13-14). Users are considered the central focus and facts and meanings are the results of social process (Almirall

et al., 2012, p.13-14). The methodology consists of four phases aimed at understanding the context where the technology will be adopted and emphasizing the changes in meanings that this adoption will produce.

The object of the project is drawing the positive changes to Deajeon citizens with software technologies. Going through the Living Labs process with Deajeon people, NIPA and DICA wanted to understand what kind of problem they really have, and draw the necessary and effective software solution. In this sense, we decided to apply adapted version of iLab.o's methodology to the Deajeon Living Lab projects.

Figure 1. Adapted iLab.o's methodology

2 Contextualization

The contextualization phase aimed to get the issue relevant information. The information was used to organize a group of stakeholders for the project process (Almirall et al., 2012, p.13-14). To collect the information sufficiently, in this phase, we conducted ① Documentary Survey, ② Deajeon City officials Interview, ③ Issue-relevant-spot investigation and Fact-check, ④ 1st Professional Group Discussion and Citizen Survey, ⑤ 2nd Professional Group Discussion and Panel Group Define. In this process, we focused on having a good grasp what are the real issues deajeon citizens have and who are the issue relevant stakeholders.

i) Documentary Survey

To grasp the need of Deajeon Citizen preliminary, survey reports, statistical data, and

policy materials that were published by Deajeon City within two years were reviewed. As a result of the literature review, sixty two themes of Deajeon City were listed-up. These were categorized into six fields (industry, culture, transportation, community welfare, senior citizens, environmental pollution). Then, DICA found out that the six fields were relevant with twenty two departments at Deajeon City Hall.

ii) Deajeon City official Interview

In accordance with the documentary survey analysis, managers at the twenty two departments were interviewed. During the interview, we inquired what policies they conducted, what kind of inconveniences that citizens asked to them, how much the inconveniences were resolved. Then, we identified the issue of each department and the stakeholders of such issues.

iii) Issue-relevant-spot investigation and Fact-check

Based upon interviews, people in charge of Living Lab in DICA visited the issue relevant spots, and did interview with the stakeholders at the spots. Conducting on-the-spot investigation, they did cross-check the analysis of documentary survey and official interview with real situation. Through this activity, they checked whether the information from documentary survey and city official interview was true or not.

iv) 1st Professional Group Discussion and Citizen Survey

The professional group was organized with people from various fields (public administration, engineering, economist, business administration, statistics etc.). They discussed about urgency, feasibility, and influence of the issues gathered from the above a, b, and c phases. Going through five discussions, 4 priority issues - residential environment improvement, public transportation, school violence, senior citizen safety - were defined. And the survey to identify the severity and causes of those issues was designed by the professional group. For two weeks, we conducted a survey of 1,000 Deajeon citizens aged 15 years or older, and analyzed the specific issue condition and inconvenience etc.

v) 2nd Professional Group Discussion and Defining Panel Group

As the last phase of Contextualization, based upon the analysis above mentioned in a, b, c, and d phases, the professional group compared with what kinds of problems happens now (real situation), and how do citizens think what problem they have (perception). Based upon this analysis, considering the severity of issues and the feasibility to resolve, the professional group discussed about the above survey results, and selected residential environment improvement as a top priority issue to be resolved. Then, they identified issue relevant stakeholders, and defined the details of the living Lab panel organization.

Figure 2. Citizen Survey Result

3 Concretisation

Almirall et al. (2012, p.13-14) state that the key element in this phase is capturing the issue condition that can be later compared with the changed condition with the introduction of the new technology or the innovation to be validated. In this regard, during the Living Lab process, we tried to define the real issue condition that should be resolved, and draw the positive stakeholders' participants efficiently.

To make specific issue condition to get solved and to define the problem Living Lab solve, DICA organized the panel of Living Lab with local residents, local government associates, NGOs, and professionals from various fields.

At the beginning of DICA Living Lab, when the panels exchanged their opinion and shared their ideas, they provided much unconfirmed and false information. Some wanted to bring personal complaints to the table, and some talked about the issue condition which had already resolved. Caused of the difference of individual view point, sometime small conflicts were aroused between panels.

To reduce inefficiency of co-works and to make them understand what the Living Lab is, DICA - as a facilitator - provided a program that introduced the concept and cases

of Living Labs. In addition, to make the panels more easily interchange each thoughts and opinion to explore the solution, DICA also provided “Design Thinking” - a problem solving methodology that emphasizes user’s participation on research and development - training program to them. Consequently, as the Living Labs processed, the participation of panels was more active, and their communication became more focused on the issue Living Lab deals with.

Figure 3. Living Labs & Design Thinking Training

Through these efforts, the top priority problem of Living Labs was defined as ‘The Household Wastes Treatment in Old Town. Household Wastes should be separated to recyclable, non-recyclable, and food waste. In old town, waste was not properly separated, and also not collected in time. These make spoil the residential environment, and cause pollution and safety accident.

Figure 4. The Household Wastes Disposals in Old Town

Panels reviewed the materials from contextualization phase, and shared their experiences, thoughts, and opinions. Simultaneously, they visited the most serious spot “Shinsung-dong” to grasp the real specific problem condition. They met 250 residents and interviewed them.

During the visit, panels on Living Labs, Design Thinking and NGO made residents actively give their opinion. Local government officials made residents notice the relevant information they wanted to get. Technicians considered how technology could be used to solve the problem.

With this visit, panels summarized the causes of the problem that residents pointed out. Many residents did not have enough information how to separate the waste, and they did not know where the waste should be put out. Also, they confused the time to collect the separated waste.

Figure 5. Drawing solution process

As a result, panels agreed that the most effective way to resolve the inconvenience in short time was distributing software service application that provide the information – how to separate, where the waste is put out, the waste collection schedule.

DICA has made action plans for Deajeon City ICT research and development policies. They have a lot of experiences making and conducting software research and development project. Drawing co-work from panels, they designed requirement specification for the application that would be able to resolve the problem. A local software company was selected to develop the application, and the prototype development was completed in Dec. 2017.

Figure 5. The requirement specification for the application & the prototype application

4 Implementation and Feedback

The test and validation in real life was carried out in the implementation phase. In the feedback phase, the ex post measurement was conducted. The results were compared with those obtained in the contextualization and implementation phases and used to infer and produce recommendations on the concrete diffusion and implementation of the technology (Almirall et al., 2012, p.13-14).

Deajeon City and DICA selected Shinsung-dong, as a testbed. Since the first quarter of 2018, the application which provide the information – how to separate, where the

waste is put out, the waste collection schedule etc. – has been distributed to Shinsung-dong residents.

As the distribution of the app was done recently, we don't find rapid changes that the application makes. However, during this phase, the more feedbacks panels gather and have a communication with users (residents), the newer service demand and idea are drawn. As the phase is processed, users' commitments to Living Lab have been grown. They positively recognize Living Lab as a place where they are able to talk about their problems with local government decision makers, and actively share their experiences and opinions. Residents want that Living Lab deals with other local community issues.

In addition, in the process of implementation, the wastes collectors asked the software application for them. This was discussed on Living Labs, and DICA Living Lab has begun to design requirement specification for the application that senses the condition of piling up and give the information to the collectors. Besides the waste issue, DICA also accept the opinions from stakeholders (panels, residents etc.) that Living Lab should be applied to other issues. They make a plan to build a big data system to draw social issues and define problem for local community more precisely.

5 Conclusion

As a result of conducting Living Lab project for one year, we identify that the followings are important to enhance stakeholders' commitments and Living Lab efficiency.

First, the shared concept and objective of Living Labs is the efficient way to give Living Labs motivation to stakeholders. As mentioned above, at the beginning phase, inefficient communication and conflicts among stakeholders existed. We resolved such conditions with Living Labs and Design Thinking training program. With the program, we tried to make understood stakeholders what they do, what kinds of result they can draw, how they make changes to their community with Living Labs. The more clear-cut mission Living Lab facilitators give to stakeholders, the stronger reasons they commitment to Living Lab are formed.

Second, the on-spot investigation is the way of filtering inefficiency for Living Labs. In Contextualization and Concretization phase, we visited issue-relevant-spot to define what condition is real problem by checking whether what we discussed and analyzed with stakeholders. Going through the on-spot investigation, some distorted or polluted

information can be filtered. It is also very helpful to gather enough resources to decide for setting priorities among the several issues. Furthermore, by communicating with people on the spot, many ideas and issues - not be discussed, but should be dealt – can be gathered. In this regard, the on-spot investigation is a good information filtering tool, as well as an ideation method.

Third, data is the key to draw real issues. In the processing contextualization and concretization, DICA Living Lab tried to compare the reality with the perception of people to define real problem. People would sense their condition more or less serious than actual condition. Data, such as statistical data, data from e-government etc., can be the criteria to determine real situation. In this project, we used such data to check out fact condition and to filter distorted information. Defining real problem is the phase of building a Living Lab project objective. The use of data can be helpful to set a direction Living Lab heads to. In recent, big data technology have been rapidly enhanced, and widely used in various fields. Considering this big wave and the Living Lab experience, DICA begins to build a big data system for Living Labs.

As a short implementation period, we are not able to find out the drastic changes Living Lab lead to though, we did many experimental attempts with a systematic Living Labs framework. As a result, some factors that make enhanced commitments of each stakeholders and Living Lab Efficiency – sharing Living Lab concept and cases with panels, problem solving methodology (ex. design thinking) training program etc. - are identified. To build knowledge to make an advancement of Living Labs, the details of the above founding should be dealt in later studies.

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